

CURING KINETIC AND PROPERTIES OF MeHHPA /HYDANTOIN EPOXY RESIN SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The new containing nitrogen epoxy that is called hydantoin epoxy resin is synthesized, its chemical structures were characterized by FTIR, NMR and hydantoin epoxy resin is cured by methylhexahydrophthalic anhydride (MeHHPA). Non-isothermal DSC followed the curing reaction to study the curing process and to evaluate curing the kinetic parameters. The curing process temperatures such as gelation temperature (T_{gel})=104.5°C, curing temperature (T_p)=153.4°C and post-curing (T_{treat})=172.4°C were acquired by extrapolation. The kinetic parameters of the MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin system curing process were determined by isoconversional method. A two-parameter (m, n) autocatalytic model was found by Máke for kinetic analysis to describe the cure kinetic of the MeHHPA /hydantoin epoxy resin. No-isothermal DSC curve obtained using the experimental data show agreement with calculated curve of autocatalytic model.

Keywords: hydantoin epoxy resin, kinetic, kinetic model function

1. Introduction

Epoxy resins with outstanding properties are one of the most widely used thermosetting polymers in automobile industries, shipbuilding, aerospace and laminates as adhesives, coatings and matrices of high performance composite materials. The widely used epoxy resins are mainly the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), which exhibits a fire risk in application. Conventional method have two way to get the flame-retardant materials. One is adoption of halogenated compounds with epoxy resin, in order to obtain DGEBA flame-retardant materials. Another is using the diglycidyl ether of tetrabromobisphenol A directly. However, bromine-containing epoxy resins and halogenated compounds in DGEBA epoxy resin release corrosive and toxic chemical substances during combustion, which effect on the environment and human health^[1].

Recently, in consideration of environmental problems, halogen-free retardant epoxy resins have become a subject of considerable attention from scientists and engineers, especially laminate. Silicon, phosphorus and nitrogen are regarded as an environment-friendly flame retardant element, because it can reduce more harmful influences on the environment than current materials that contains halogen atoms (e.g. bromine or chlorine)^[2-4,7].

Although these phosphorus-containing epoxy resins exhibited good flame-retardancy, they existed low heat resistance, low glass transition temperature and low crosslink density. Furthermore, phosphorus-containing compounds are

detrimental to the environment and human health. Green manufacture of epoxy resin within phosphorus-containing compounds and management of waste phosphorus-containing epoxy products should be research deeply in the future. Silicon-containing epoxy resins possess not only excellent water resistance, but also preferable flame retardation. However silicon-containing epoxy resin is provided with low glass transition temperature and low interlaminar shearing strength of laminates.

We have synthesized hydantoin epoxy resin, and used methylhexahydrophthalic anhydride (MeHHPA) as curing agent, which is called MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resins. The method and mathematical expression of the curing kinetics are important to control the reactions and optimize the physical properties of the final products. So far, there have been various techniques to study the cure kinetics of thermosetting resins. And in this work, the DSC technique was introduced to investigate the kinetics of the MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin, which was cured under nonisothermal conditions.

2. CURING KINETIC ANALYSIS

The reaction rate of the kinetic curing process for resin system can be described by Eq. (1)

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(T)f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

Where $K(T)$ is temperature-dependent reaction rate constant, $f(\alpha)$ is kinetic model function, and T is the absolute temperature. The rate constant is temperature dependent, which conforms to Arrhenius equation, as Eq. (2)

$$K(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where A is pre-exponential factor and E_a is apparent activation energy. In non-isothermal conditions, when the temperature rise to a constant heating rate $\beta = dT/dt$, Eq. (1) can be modified as follows:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

In order to describe the behaviors of the curing kinetic, the most suitable kinetic model should be determined firstly. Meanwhile, the apparent activation energy (E_a) is prerequisite. But Eq.(3) has no exact analytical solution. Therefore, some necessary mathematical methods have been developed to deal with it. Two kinetic methods that are widely used to study kinetics of epoxy resin are model-fitting and model-free methods [27-31]. In the interest of avoiding the complex integration of equation (3), Friedman-Reich-Levi method and Ozawa-Flynn-Wall method are expressed in equation (4) to calculate the apparent activation energy.

$$\ln \beta = \ln\left(\frac{AE}{RG(\alpha)}\right) - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (4)$$

Once E_a is determined, Mathematical expression of $f(\alpha)$ is deduced effectively as

defined by Malek method. Two special functions, $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$, can be constructed as the criteria for kinetic model determination and parameter estimation:

$$y(\alpha) = \frac{d\alpha}{dt} e^{\chi} \quad (5)$$

$$Z(\alpha) = \pi(\chi) \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) \frac{T}{\beta} \quad (6)$$

Where $\chi = E_a/RT$, $\pi(\chi)$ is the expression of the temperature integral. As is pointed out^[5,6], $\pi(\chi)$ can be well approximated using the 4th rational expression of Senum and Yang as in Eq.(7).

$$\pi(\chi) = \frac{\chi^3 + 18\chi^2 + 88\chi + 96}{\chi^4 + 20\chi^3 + 120\chi^2 + 240\chi + 120} \quad (7)$$

$y(\alpha)$ function is proportional to $f(\alpha)$ function, which is represent the characteristic of given kinetic model. The shape and the maximum of both $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$ functions normalized within (0,1) can be used to determine the most suitable kinetic model of the curing process. Once the kinetic model is determined, other kinetic parameters could be calculated out by using the value of E_a , such as pre-exponential factor and kinetic exponents. The pre-exponential factor A was calculated according to Eq. (8):

$$A = \frac{\beta \chi_p}{T f'(\alpha_p)} \exp(\chi_p) \quad (8)$$

Where $f'(\alpha_p)$ be the differential form of the kinetic model $[df(\alpha)/d\alpha]$, α_p is the conversion corresponding to the maximum on DSC curve and p is the maximum of DSC curve.

2.1 Materials

1-chloro-2, 3-epoxypropane and 5,5'- dimethylhydantoin were purchased from beijing zhonglian chemical Co(China). Hexahydrophthalic anhydrid was purchased from Shanghai First Reagent Co. Isopropyl alcohol and sodium hydroxide were purchased from Tianjin Reagent Co.

2.2 Preparation of Hydantoin Epoxy Resin

12.8g of 5,5'-dimethylhydantoin and 20g of 1-chloro-2, 3-epoxypropane, 19.1g of isopropyl alcohol were added to a three-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, reflux condenser and a thermometer, and then stirred. After that, the NaOH was added by dropwise into the mixture in 1h and further reacted at the reflux temperature for 5h. The organic phase was distilled isopropyl alcohol, and then we got the hydantoin epoxy resin.

IR(KBr, cm^{-1}): 3500 cm^{-1} (–OH of epoxypropyl), 1769 cm^{-1} and 1708 cm^{-1} (C=O), 2985 cm^{-1} , 2938 cm^{-1} (–CH₃ of hydantoin), 849 cm^{-1} (epoxypropyl). ¹H-NMR

(CDCl₃,ppm):1.515ppm (6H, CH₃ of hydantoin), 2.60-2.98ppm (2H, CH₂ of epoxypropyl), 3.12ppm (H, CH of epoxypropyl), 3.55-3.87ppm(2H, CH₂ of N atom of hydantoin). Epoxy equivalent of hydantoin epoxy resin is 164g equiv⁻¹ and viscosity is 6.9 mPa s at 25°C. Fig 1 shows the structural formula of materials used in this research work.

Fig 1. Molecular structures of hydantoin epoxy resin and methylhexahydrophthalic anhydride

2.3 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The curing behavior of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin was examined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) Q100 from TA Instruments. The reaction mixture was cured in DSC under non-isothermal conditions at heating rates of 10, 20, and 40°C/min which was heated from 30 to 350°C in a constant flow of nitrogen of 50ml/min. The heat flow data, as a function of temperature and time, were obtained using the area under the peak of the exothermic. They were processed further to obtain a fractional conversion (α) and the rate of the reaction da/dt .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Curing Reaction of MeHHPA/Hydantoin

The curing reaction of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy can be studied by DSC at different heating rates. Fig 1 shows the DSC thermograms at 10, 20, and 40°C/min. As clearly seen, only one single and symmetric exothermic peak can be found for each non-isothermal run from 100°C—250°C, which is as a result of the MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy ring-opening addition reaction. Increasing of the heating rates not only leads to the gradually increasing of DSC peak areas but also lets DSC peak value move to high temperatures. Integration of DSC thermograms obtained

Fig 1. DSC curve of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy

Fig 2. Degree of conversion α vs temperature

information about the curing reaction shows the values of the initial curing temperature(T_i), the peak temperature (T_p), and the finishing temperature(T_f). These data on the curing reaction are listed in table1. The curing process characteristic temperatures of the resin system is important such as gelation temperature (T_{gel})= 104.5°C , curing temperature (T_{cure})= 153.4°C and post-curing(T_{treat})= 172.4°C , which were acquired by DSC extrapolation at various heating rates. Fig 2 is the variation of the degree of conversion as a function of temperature at different heating

Tab 1. The data of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin from DSC

β , $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$	T_i , $^\circ\text{C}$	T_p , $^\circ\text{C}$	T_f , $^\circ\text{C}$
10	383.3	428.2	455.6
20	397.8	442.2	477.4
40	409.5	451.7	497.8

rates, which could be obtained from integrating the DSC curves of Fig 1. On the curve of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, the conversion increased very slowly in the initial stage and rose abruptly in the range of $140.0\text{--}180.0^\circ\text{C}$, and it was almost constant in the final stage. All of the curves figured S-shape at different heating rates, and the abrupt increment in the narrow temperature range, which indicated that the auto-acceleration behavior was in MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin curing process. In the other hand increasing the heating rate enables the conversional curve to shift towards a higher temperature range, which means that increased degree of the MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin reactions will occur at a higher temperature.

3.2 Calculation of Changes in Activation Energy and Modeling of Reaction Function

Arrhenius plots from DSC scans recorded for curing samples using Eq.(4) and the same α value are straight lines, the slope of which gives the value of E_a . Plots of the natural logarithm of heating rate against the reciprocal temperature are shown in Fig.3. Average value of E_a calculated out is 95.38KJ/mol in the range $0.2 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$ by Ozawa-Flynn-Wall method. Fig.4 is the curve of variation E_a versus conversion α , it can be observed that E_a values have slight decrease with increase conversion α . This phenomenon implies that the auto-acceleration behavior was in MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin curing process because of the third amine containing in chemical structures of epoxy resin.

Fig.3 cures of $\ln\beta$ vs. $\frac{1}{T_p} \times 10^{-3}$

Fig. 4 Variation of E_a versus conversion α

Curing reaction mechanism function is an important mathematics model that requires information of curing process. As same times, mechanism function is also defined by above mentioned M \ddot{a} lek method.

Fig 5. Variation of $y(\alpha)$ function versus conversion α

Fig6. Variation of $z(\alpha)$ function versus α

The E_a values is 95.38KJ/mol that is the average of Ozawa-Flynn-Wall method calculated value, which was used to calculated both $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$. Fig5 and Fig6 represent the characteristics of curves $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$ at different curing degree

respectively. Curing degrees of peak value of $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$ curves are α_m and α_p^∞ respectively, which are used to estimate characteristic value of mechanism function.

Tab 3. The values of α_m , α_p^∞ and α_p for MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy

β , °C/min	α_m	α_p^∞	α_p
10	0.1614	0.56038	0.55041
20	0.1864	0.5018	0.48831
40	0.1075	0.5032	0.46343

α_m and α_p^∞ at different heating rate are listed in Table 3. As can be seen from Tab. 3, α_p^∞ is less than 0.632. Curing reaction process of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy can be described by the two-parameter autocatalytic kinetic model from Šestál-Berggren in Eq.(9).

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (9)$$

m and n are the kinetic exponents of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin curing reaction process. Rewriting Eq. (3) using Eq. (9) and kinetic model function exhibit as the following equation (10).

$$\ln\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} e^x\right) = \ln A + n \ln[\alpha^S (1 - \alpha)] \quad (10)$$

The kinetic exponents n is obtained by the slope of the linear dependence $\ln\left[\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} e^x\right)\right]$ versus $\ln[\alpha^S (1 - \alpha)]$ from Eq. (10), and $m = Sn$, where $S = \alpha_m / (1 - \alpha_m)$.

Tab. 4 The kinetic parameters evaluated for the curing of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin

Heating rate, °C/min	n	m	A	E
10	1.1091	0.2135	1.9557×10^{11}	
20	1.3094	0.2999	1.6856×10^{11}	
40	1.4178	0.1706	1.6398×10^{11}	
mean	1.2788	0.2135	1.7604×10^{11}	95.38Kj/mol

Kinetics parameter of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin is obtained and presented in Tab.4. According to the data presented in Tab.4, Mechanism function of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin curing reaction process is expressed as in Eq.(11).

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^{0.68} (1 - \alpha)^{1.531} \quad (11)$$

The relation of curing rate and curing degree of MeHHPA/hydantoin epoxy resin curing reaction process is expressed as in Eq.(12).

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = 1.7604 \times 10^{11} \alpha^{0.2135} (1 - \alpha)^{1.2788} \exp\left(-\frac{95380}{RT}\right) \quad (12)$$

The result of the compare between experimental data and calculated data was shown in Fig 6. It exhibits that non-isothermal DSC curve obtained by experimental data is good agreement with simulated data by autocatalytic model, but calculated data from the model were higher than the experimental results in the end of curing

reaction process. The cause of this phenomenon can be attributed to complex chemical reaction at the near end of conversion by mass transfer processes such as viscous relaxation and vitrification. That is the monomer molecules become immobile in their positions in the glassy state that results in the virtual cessation of polymerization.

Fig 6. Comparison of experimental data and simulated (red) data for MeHHPA / hydantoin epoxy resin

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